
Paper 28

JOB FAIR AND CSR

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Abstract

Socially organizing, participation and supporting Job Fairs is a mandatory obligation of all stakeholders involved towards employment generation in the economy. However, Job Fairs are also viewed with commercial intention by stakeholders for benefits or profits. A commercial approach in such a situation over runs the social patriotic agenda of societal development, economy and manpower development of a country. Though CSR (Corporate Social Responsibility) mandates organizations to conduct social activities, sponsoring or holding public job fairs or at least freewill participation in such career fairs as a social responsibility has always remained a rare sight for corporations or employers. Further presence of third-party business-oriented consultants in the market with lobbying tactics has also made government agencies responsible for holding employment fairs enticed towards favouritism. Therefore, this research investigates the differences involved in holding a Social job fair as compared with Commercial motives of participating recruiters in those fairs. The paper also propagates national and international sensitivity towards employment generation by listing out Employers' positions and standing in job fair participations for social-national-global cause and its importance with relation to CSR.

Keywords : CSR Job Fair, Social Job Fair, Social Employment Fair, Social Career Fair

I. Introduction :

Career fairs continue to be a popular method for employers looking for human talent and they should be considerate for any parties organizing the same for them especially Not for Profit Firms, NGO's or HEI's. However, there is also a paid outsourced practice of holding customized job fairs by commercial event management firms. Opportunistically, Organizations in order to minimize operating expenditure depend on social organizations for holding job fair, but pressurize them through predatory tactics to use the platform for filling manpower from society for business requirements (Experience Interviews). This action conflicts the generally perceived Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in the eyes of general public. Thus, this study analyses the relationship significance of a Pure CSR Action with a Commercial Motive in holding recruitments in a JOB FAIR.

II. Objectives of the Research :

This study thrives to accomplish following noble objectives :

- (1) To understand the commercial motive of business organizations participating in job fairs.

- (2) To propagate the importance of aligning recruitment and selection with Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR).
- (3) To educate the significance of social cause at Job Fairs to business organizations.

III. Research Methodology :

Direct Opinion Interviews and Experience Interviews were conducted with a Focused Group of HR from select 30 Business Organizations. The responses so obtained was analysed for findings and thereby conclusions.

IV. Analysis and Interpretations :

Following is the concluded Summary of Discussions related to the topic :

- (1) HRM Function is not a part of CSR but a part of primary business function for profit organizations. Therefore, commercial and professional expectations are demanded with job fair organizers.
- (2) Job Fair is one of the sources of manpower recruitment methods.
- (3) There is no mandated rules or law to be followed in holding and participating in job fairs to be viewed as a social cause.
- (4) Holding Job Fairs is the responsibility of social institutions like Not for Profit Organizations, District Employment Centres, District Industries Centre, NGO's, Trust and Foundations, Educational Institutions with social standing and NOT Business Organizations.
- (5) Business Organizations do not want to hold job fairs as it does not want to incur expenditure from its profit centre. Job Applications are welcome instead.
- (6) Confirmed participating business organizations can cancel participations in job fair even in last minute citing business urgency or meetings.
- (7) The law says a company can undertake its CSR activities only through a registered trust, a registered society or a non-profit firm. Hence, it is extra efforts and expenditure to promote recruitments when it is easy to promote the same as a business function instead.

V. Findings :

Upon analysis and interpretation of above summary of discussions following findings were deduced :

- (1) Organizations are not favourably directed towards joining the social cause of employment generation in job fairs from a CSR Perspective. They hold Organizers accountable if no candidate walks in to their centre in the venue.
- (2) Lack of uniform law across organizations to align Employment Opportunity Provision as a CSR does not exist making organizations to approach business as usual approach in job fairs.
- (3) Organization Officials demand in exorbitantly hospitality demands from fair organizers to provide travel, food and accommodation for job fair participations.
- (4) Purposefully provide negative feedback for character assassination of job fair organizers to obtain publicity.
- (5) Social Enterprises or Not for Profit Organizations find it hard to bring job seekers and business minded companies bring together for a social job fair.

VI. Extended Suggestions :

- (1) Keeping in view of Employment Creation, Government should make Employment Opportunity Provision (EOP) as an integral part of CSR through appropriate amendments in the Schedule VII, Companies Act 2013.
- (2) Minimum number of Participation in Job Fair should be made mandatory in a financial or business year as CSR through appropriate amendments in the Schedule VII, Companies Act 2013.
- (3) Business Organizations should also take Onus in promoting their company in the job fair for better job seeker visibility and shoulder support with organizers. For example, like supplying their flyers, banners, business cards with recruiter contact details as well as SPONSORSHIP for better cause.
- (4) Companies should start by listing out all points of interaction with society across its value chain to derive a complete list of possible initiatives it could execute. The next step is to rank each of the items on this long list on the basis of the extent of social impact and impact on the firm's long-term competitiveness.

VII. Conclusions :

To conclude, employment creation efforts still lay outside the gambit of CSR for Business Organizations. For Business Organizations, Employment Opportunity efforts through Job Fair are primary business requirement initiatives and not social cause. Pre-existing Industry Academia Gap at Market is due to a lack of alignment of mandatory employment opportunity creation requirement on to CSR laws. Job Fairs could be a Social Cause for Organizations from Publicity and Marketing perspective only. Moreover, there is tax benefit for companies actually undertaking CSR activities for specific activities only, which is unfair.

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